

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR IMPACT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The introduction of modern innovative technologies is a positive step for enterprises. Effective informatization of innovative technologies significantly increases macroeconomic indicators and socio-economic development processes of the enterprise, which leads to an increase in the quality and level of management decisions, the efficiency of information processes and services, which in turn improves socio-economic, scientific, technical, improves cultural and other indicators of life. The introduction of information in all processes and the development of modern innovative technologies will have a positive effect on the growth of the gross domestic product.

Keywords: global, technology, market, innovation, information, price, finance, enterprise, economy.

Globalization and technical progress require increasing their interdependence, while the informatization of innovative technologies, which allow access to international markets of new goods and services, is becoming increasingly important. The use of innovations has a significant impact on accelerating the structural restructuring of the country's economy and increasing its investment attractiveness, competitiveness and financial stability. In modern conditions, it is of great importance to create favorable conditions for informatization of innovative technologies that ensure macroeconomic development. The information process covers almost all areas of society and is associated with the use of the latest innovative technologies. Information plays an important role and is one of the most important driving forces for the enterprise.

Innovative development is characterized by shifting the main attention to the use of radically new progressive technologies, transition to the production of high-tech products, advanced organizational and management solutions in innovative activities, which depends on both micro and macroeconomic trends. It helps establish and reveal the benefits of new types of economy that conserve resources and promote zero-waste technologies. The ecological risk of human activities, the implementation of various types of activities on an industrial scale creates a system of negative actions on the

environment. Therefore, creating prospects for improving the existence of the population and the environment, as well as minimizing the negative consequences of the depletion of natural resources and environmental pollution as a result of the rapid socio-economic development of mankind, is a necessary condition for the development and application of the principles of circular economy. Current problems of substantiating the benefits of circular economy, as well as for the formation of a new model of the economy that integrates components and business informatization, are necessary for adaptation in industry, various types of transport, and in the process of human activity. The problems of environmental protection and reduction of negative impact are the main conditions for processing and disposal of waste. In this context, circular economy principles are an important tool for their operation, saving resources and saving money on production and processing costs. The processes listed above are indicators of macroeconomic development that are directly related to the level of economic growth and stability. The main goal of the research is to identify the main macroeconomic trends that are directly related to the informatization of innovative technologies in the conditions of the circular economy, which will allow more effective use of tools, methods and forms of the circular economy. In this regard, the study of macroeconomic trends is the basis for justifying the directions (components) and processes of their interaction. The importance of the concept of the circular economy as a way of achieving high macroeconomic development is ensured by the application of the principles of informatization of innovative technologies at all stages of economic development. At the base of the consistent change of technological orders lies the main innovation. The totality of technologies at each moment of time can be represented by technological structures summarizing the cycle of social reproduction. Each of them represents a specific feature, the way certain order technologies work creates a new quality, stable technology, which is dominated by a characteristic principle.

Innovative technologies are of great importance in economic development and global reforms. These technologies play an important role in creating opportunities to create innovations, automate production processes, produce products with better quality and efficiency, improve services, and strengthen customer relationships.

Innovative technologies have a massive beneficial effect on economic development. These technologies make it possible to produce products at a higher quality and at a lower cost, which increases sales by providing consumers with cheaper and better quality products. Also, innovative technologies open up opportunities for innovation and use in other areas, which help create new jobs and expand economic diversification. .

Innovative technologies are also important in global reforms. With their help, companies will be successful in the world market with their services and products and will have the necessary opportunities for their development in international markets.

Also, innovative technologies facilitate business activities in markets related to global customers and help to improve services.

In addition, innovative technologies are the basis of the latest modern economic models and are among the most important sources of economic development. These technologies increase the speed of economic development, strengthen innovative activities and allow the creation of innovations. Also, innovative technologies lead to important developments in various areas of economic development (for example, transport, medicine, energy, etc.).

At the same time, innovative technologies are of great importance in economic development, and their development and application are key conditions for global economic development.

Since innovative technologies are of great importance for economic development, there are several actors responsible for their development and application. The following officers are in charge of innovative technologies and their role in economic development:

1. Minister of Industry and Innovation: This ministry is responsible for the development of innovative technologies and innovations in the industrial sector, strengthening of innovative activities among companies and entrepreneurs, application of innovations and financial support for innovative projects. deals with giving.

2. Minister of Information and Communications: This ministry is responsible for the development of innovations and innovations in the field of information technology, communications, the application of innovations in the field of information technology, the expansion of Internet and telecommunication services, and the strengthening of customer relations.

3. Minister of Transport and Logistics: This ministry is responsible for the development of innovative technologies and innovations in the field of transport, application of innovations in the field of transport, automation of transport systems and improvement of logistics processes.

4. Minister of Energy: This ministry is responsible for promoting innovative technologies in the field of energy and energy consumption, optimizing energy consumption, ensuring energy security and upgrading energy systems.

5. Minister of Medicine and Health Care: This ministry is engaged in the development of innovative technologies and innovations in the field of medicine, improvement of health services, automation of medical systems, expansion of telemedicine services.

These tasks are of great importance for mastering innovative technologies and their place in economic development, and it is necessary to provide them with financial resources, scientific and technical personnel, entrepreneurial directions and other

indicators. Organizational issues are also important for the coordination of their activities and the implementation of innovative projects.

Currently, innovation is becoming one of the most characteristic features of economic development. Not long ago, this name reminded of something exotic, unknown and not very clear even among professionals, but now the innovation itself and its concepts are rapidly conquering the world. The international capital market, which plays a significant role in the innovation process and turns innovation into a strategic resource for enterprises, is expanding, and new financial structures are helping it in this regard.

The experience of developed countries shows that innovation is often hindered by direct negative attitudes and attitudes of people. However, a paradoxical situation is developing in Uzbekistan, that is, the whole society expresses positive attitude and support to innovative processes.

The aim of the research work is to help increase the potential and efficiency of the system through innovative development of the economy and the creation of new entrepreneurs. The tasks of the research are researching the stages of increasing competitiveness and productivity in the industry and justifying its specific features; to stimulate the increase of the share of high-tech products, to increase the production and to increase the share in the structure of production and export, to identify the factors affecting the expansion of the use of innovative technologies and advanced management.

If we compare the innovative processes in our country with the situation in developed countries, now the developed countries of the world have been under the influence of the innovative economy and the fifth technological cycle (long wave) for more than 15 years. What should countries do that are only able to enter the fifth wave, and even beyond?

Will they reach these countries first by starting their scientific research in new high-tech directions? Apparently, this is very problematic. However, this prevents these countries, especially in our country, from using the technologies created by other countries and using them in the development of their economy, trying to surpass developed countries by creating as many conditions as possible for foreign investments to enter the country. Some time ago, this experiment was carried out in Japan, South Korea and other countries. In fact, the opportunities provided by innovation and the positive aspects of globalization were first of all captured by South-East Asian countries (often called "tigers"), such as South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore, as well as the Celts. The "tiger" is Ireland, one of the leaders in the field of innovation. These countries can serve as a paradigm for Uzbekistan, because our country, with its small market, poor traditional resources, can only develop successfully if it chooses an innovative path using its competitive unique non-traditional resources.

It is also worth noting the concept of the so-called "European innovation paradox" from the world experience - on the one hand, when assessing the share of investments in education and science in the GDP, as well as the percentage of highly educated people in the population in most countries of the European Union, the USA or even better than Japan. Europe also surpasses them in terms of indicators of scientific potential (for example, the number of Nobel Prize winners, SCI publications, number of scientists with doctoral degrees). Nevertheless, the productivity of the economy in the European Union is twice as low as that of the United States, and its trade balance with the United States is negative. Students from different parts of the world are trying to study in higher educational institutions of the USA. The United States itself is a very successful country in the use of innovation, commercializing knowledge created not only in its own country, but also around the world. The best specialists in the field of higher education and research (project managers, researchers, highly educated technology specialists) move to the USA. Europe is betting on training and higher education in US companies. According to these and similar facts, the term "European innovation paradox" also appeared.

A new trend in the use of innovations has formed in Uzbekistan's industry. Until then, industries related to the processing of natural resources with the use of cheap labor dominated. However, today Uzbekistan aims for a completely new approach to the use of natural resources. A clear example of this is the new UzGTL plant, which is dedicated to the production of products with high added value based on the deep processing of natural gas. Thanks to such large projects, Uzbekistan is gradually abandoning the export of raw natural gas and reducing the import of oil products. This indicates that a significant contribution is being made to strengthening our energy independence. This UzGTL complex, which is considered one of the largest investment projects not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the CIS countries, is also an example of innovative production. Also, one of the most modern and innovative in the territory of the CIS is the central control panel of the enterprise and the central factory laboratory. The new enterprise has the capacity to process 3.6 billion cubic meters of natural gas per year and produce 1.5 million tons of finished products, jet kerosene, diesel fuel, naphtha, liquefied gas, based on GTL, that is, "gas to liquid" technology. Until now, such a plant has been established in only 4 countries in the world: Qatar, Nigeria, South Africa and Malaysia. Here, oil products and hydrocarbon raw materials are produced annually, with a total value of 1 billion US dollars or more than 12.8 trillion soms. Obtaining value-added products from natural gas based on GTL technology is carried out in three stages. Modern types of fuel made on the basis of this technology are environmentally friendly and clean. This, in turn, corresponds to the principle of not harming nature, which has become an urgent issue today. Take GTL diesel for example. GTL diesel, which has a high technical specification and almost no sulfur

content, emits no significant emissions into the atmosphere. Also, GTL kerosene offers airlines a safe and cost-effective way to reduce emissions.

To sum up, in modern enterprises engaged in innovative entrepreneurship and introducing innovations using foreign experience in the production process, compared to traditional enterprises, wages are 2-3 times higher, work productivity is 2 times higher, especially for employees. The quality of life and welfare compared to before shows the positive aspects of today's innovative economic reforms. But along with the progress being made, there are also problems to be solved. In particular: our entrepreneurs do not have sufficient skills in business management; inability of employees to quickly absorb news; they cannot adequately assess internal and external risks, the need for innovation and their position in the world market; insufficient attention is paid to the development of enterprises, increasing competitiveness; there are also many problems in creating a business environment and developing a structure to encourage innovation. In solving these problems, we consider the following proposals and recommendations to be appropriate: the role of private business in the process of financing scientific research should be increased, which will give an incentive to increase the efficiency of investments in research and development; it is necessary to increase the level of investments necessary for innovation and strengthen competition;

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